

by usual recrystallisation procedure. Finally preparative tlc method was adopted to get two homogeneous constituents A and B. The compound A was identical with friedelin as seen by Co-tlc and by Co-glc study. (Ret time 9.5 mins at 278° column: 3% SE 30 on gas chrom-Z, 60-80 mesh.) The second compound B had m.p. 168°. The mixed melting point and the super-impossible IR spectrum showed its identity with β -amyrene.

The fraction from next eluate was triacontanol. The last fraction was β -sitosterol. The amount of β -sitosterol isolated was exceptionally quite large in amount.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Mr. Pannalal Koley of CDRI, Lucknow for his ungrudging assistance.

References

1. R. D. BENNETT, SHUI-TZEKO and E. HEFTMANN, *Phytochemistry*, 1966, 5, 231.
2. H. ASHMawi, A. A. HUSSEIN and M. H. SHAKER, *Bull. Fac. Sci.*, 1955, 61, 12 *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 16743a.
3. M. S. EL. RIDI, L. A. STRAIT and M. H. ABOL WAFa, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1952, 39, 317; *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 13381.

Chemical Constituents of *Ligustrum nelgherrense* Dalz and Gibs var. *obovata**

H. S. GARG and N. M. KHANNA

Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow

Manuscript received 2 September 1978, revised 23 July 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

LIGUSTRUM nelgherrense Dalz and Gibs var. *obovata* (Oleaceae) grows extensively as a shrub or small tree in the Western peninsula on the Ghats from Bombay southwards to the higher hills of the Konkan and is very common on the Mahabaleshwar plateau.

Under the programme of screening Indian plants over a wide range of biological activity at this Institute it was found that 50 per cent EtOH extract of the whole plant showed anticancer activity¹. The presence of stigmasterol in its roots was reported earlier². The present communication describes the isolation and identification of kaempferitrin, taraxerol, β -sitosterol and β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol from the whole plant in yields ranging from 0.01 to 0.05 per cent.

The alcoholic extract (90-95 per cent) of the air dried whole plant was successively fractionated into benzene, ethylacetate and butanol soluble and aqueous fractions. The ethylacetate and butanol soluble fractions showed marginal activity against P₃₈₈

Lymphocytic leukaemia in mice and were further studied. The butanol soluble fraction on repeated column chromatography over silica gel yielded kaempferitrin³ (I) (3,7-dirhamnosyl kaempferol), C₂₇H₃₀O₄, m.p. 218-20° in 0.01 per cent yield, from the ethylacetate methanol eluted fractions, crystallising as pale yellow needles from methanol. It responded to Shinoda test for flavonoids. The UV spectra showed $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 264 and 345 nm, $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH} + \text{AlCl}_3}$ 273, 298 and 374 nm (indicating the presence of a free C-5 hydroxyl group). On acid hydrolysis I yielded kaempferol, m.p. 270-72° (dec.) (lit m.p. 273-75°) and two moles of rhamnose. The observed difference in the m.p. 218-20° (lit³ m.p. 202-203°) of (I) may be attributed to the solvent used for crystallisation⁴. The identity was further supported by its NMR spectrum at 90 MHz in DMSO-d₆. The signals due to two methyl protons of the two rhamnose units attached at C-3 and C-7 in I, appeared as doublets at 85 and 112 cps (J, 6.5 Hz). The glycosyl protons in turn appeared at 530 and 553 cps. The other protons of the rhamnose molecules crowded as broad peaks between 300 to 425 cps. The protons of the aromatic nuclei of the flavonol moiety could be assigned as follows: The protons at C-6 and C-8 showing *meta* coupling, appeared at 645 and 675 cps respectively as narrow doublets (J, 2Hz). The two doublets of two protons each at 690 and 780 cps (J, 10Hz) may be assigned to 3', 5' and 2', 6' protons respectively showing *ortho* couplings.

The ethylacetate soluble fraction on chromatography separately over silica gel column using benzene, benzene-ethylacetate mixture as eluents afforded colourless needles of taraxerol, m.p. 278-80°, C₃₀H₅₀O, crystallising from methanol; $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH group); acetate C₃₂H₅₂O₂, m.p. 302-304° (m. mp and superimposable IR spectra with that of an authentic sample). Further elution of the column with ethyl acetate and ethylacetate-methanol mixture yielded a sterol glycoside, m.p. 292-96° (d), C₃₅H₅₈O₆ in 0.02 per cent yield and crystallising as microcrystalline needles from methanol. On acid hydrolysis it gave one mole each of β -sitosterol and glucose. Its identity as β -D-glucoside of β -sitosterol was confirmed by m. mp and superposable IR spectra. The earlier fractions eluted with benzene afforded in poor yields free β -sitosterol as well.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. Gopal Misra, National Botanic Gardens, Lucknow, for an authentic sample of taraxerol. The collection of plant material and anti-cancer testing was carried by the unit of this Institute receiving NIH grants.

References

1. M. L. DHAR, M. M. DHAR, B. N. DHAWAN, B. N. MEHROTRA, R. C. SRIMAL and J. S. TANDON, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1973, 11, 43.

* CDRI Communication No. 2472

2. B. ANJANEYULU, V. BABU RAO, A. K. GANGULY, T. R. GOVINDACHARI, B. S. JOSHI, V. N. KAMAT, A. H. MANMADE, P. A. MOHAMED, A. D. RAHIMTULA, A. K. SAKSENA, D. S. VARDE and N. VISWANATHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 237.
3. F. M. DEAN, "Naturally Occurring Oxygen Ring Compounds", Butterworths, London 1963, p. 324.
4. S. HATTORI, *Nature*, 1951, 168, 788.

Chemical Constituents of *Woodfordia fruticosa* Linn.

JAGDISH S. CHAUHAN, SANTOSH K. SRIVASTAVA* and SAVITRI D. SRIVASTAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 19 January 1978, revised 12 April 1979, accepted 6 October 1979

WOODFORDIA fruticosa Linn (Lythraceae) is a shrub and found throughout India. The plant is reputed for its medicinal values^{1,2}. A perusal of literature revealed that no work has been reported on this plant. The present investigation deals with the isolation and identification of the constituents from flowers. The identity of each compound was established by comparison (m.m.p., IR, co-TLC) with authentic samples.

The air dried flowers (1.5 kg) of the plant, collected in Allahabad, were extracted with petroleum ether (40-60°). The extract was concentrated to 100 ml. On cooling it gave a yellowish coloured solid (500 mg) (Fraction-A). Then the defatted flowers were refluxed with ethanol (120 hr). The ethanolic extract was concentrated and poured into distilled water. The water soluble portion was extracted with ether (Fraction-B) and then ethyl acetate (Fraction-C) separately in a liquid-liquid extractor.

Hecogenin: Fraction-A, on column chromatography over neutral alumina and elution with methanol, gave a solid which on crystallization (aqueous methanol), furnished colourless white needles of hecogenin³ (300 mg) C₂₇H₄₂O₄, m.p. 253°, M⁺ 430. It gave positive Liebermann-Burchardt⁴ and Salkowski⁵ tests. ν_{max} (KBr) 3450 (OH), 2940 (CH₃), 1705 (CO), 1460 (C-CH₃) and 1350-875 cm⁻¹ (spiro-ketal side chain) etc., acetate, m.p. 250° (lit. m.p. 252°); 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 281-82° d. (lit. m.p. 282° d).

Mesoinositol: Fraction-B, on column chromatography over deactivated alumina and elution with ethanol, gave a creamish white solid (200 mg) which on crystallization (ethanol/petroleum ether mixture) gave colourless needles of mesoinositol⁶, C₆H₁₂O₆, m.p. 225-27°. ν_{max} (KBr) 3640 (OH), 1032 cm⁻¹ (OH) etc., acetate, m.p. 215° (lit. m.p. 216°), benzoate, m.p. 256° (lit. m.p. 258°).

* Correspondence Address: Dr. S. K. Srivastava, Chemistry Department, Saugar University, Saugar (M.P.) 470 003.

Flavone glycosides: Fraction-C, dark reddish coloured compound (2 g), on column chromatography over silica gel and elution with methanol: water in a gradient from (4:6) to (1:9) gave a mixture of three flavonoid compounds. This was resolved by preparative TLC with ethyl acetate: methanol in a different proportions into Band-I, Band-II and Band-III which afforded respectively Quercetin-3-rhamnoside⁷ (120 mg) as yellow needles (from aqueous methanol), m.p. 182-84°; naringenin-7-glucoside⁸ (110 mg) as golden yellow needles (from aqueous ethanol), m.p. 225-26° and kaempferol-3-glucoside⁹ (140 mg) as small yellow needles (from aqueous ethanol), m.p. 172-73°.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. R. D. Tiwari, Head, Chemistry Department, Allahabad University, Allahabad, for providing authentic samples and the U.G.C., New Delhi, for research fellowship to one of us (SKS).

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA., *Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants*, 1956, 259.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU., *Indian Medicinal Plants*, 1940, 2, 1074.
3. R. E. MARKER, R. B. WAGNER, P. R. ULSHAFFER, E. L. WITTBECKER, D. P. J. GOLDSMITH and C. H. ROUF., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 1199; 1947, 69, 2167.
4. C. LIEBERMANN., *Ber. deutsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1885, 1804.
5. E. SALKOWSKI., *Hoppe-Seylers Z.*, 1908, 57, 521.
6. S. BROWNSTEIN., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 1606.
7. A. G. PERKIN and A. E. EVEREST., *The Natural Organic Colouring Matters.*, Longmann Green & Co., London.
8. W. RAHMAN, M. ILLYAS and N. HAMEED., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 278.
9. T. NAKABAYASHI., *J. Agr. Chem. Soc.*, Japan, 1952, 26, 539.

Chemical Constituents of *Anemone narcissiflora* Linn

K. P. TIWARI*, M. MASOOD and Y. K. S. RATHORE

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, India

Manuscript received 12 January 1978, revised 7 December 1978, accepted 6 October 1979

A large number of saponins¹ have been isolated from various species of the genus *Anemone*, but surprisingly, complete structures of these saponins have not been elucidated. The authors, therefore, undertook the chemical analysis of *Anemone narcissiflora* Linn.² with a view to make a detailed study of saponin and other constituents of the plant. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of oleanolic acid, betulinic acid, β -sitosterol, β -amyirin and a new saponin olean-3-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl- $\Delta^{1,2}$ -ene-28-oic acid from *A. narcissiflora*.